

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha).
- With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

White Ponni rice in Tamil Nadu

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White Ponni was introduced in India from Malaysia. It is a tall indica from Taichung 65 Mayung Ebos 80 and matures in 135 d. It has medium-slender white grains with good cooking quality.

White Ponni is popular for transplanting and direct seeding in Tamil Nadu. We compared it and other popular varieties at PES in samba (Jul-Aug to Nov-Dec) and late samba (Sep-

Oct to Jan-Feb).

For direct-seeding trials, seeds were sown when rains began and the fields later were flooded (see table). The crop received 10 t of farmyard manure/ha and 50 kg N/ha was topdressed in equal splits 30 and 45 d after seeding. Transplanted trials with tall indicas received a basal 15-14 kg PK/ha, and 52 kg N/ha was topdressed in equal splits 20 and 40 d after transplanting. Semidwarfs received a basal dose of 22-42 kg PK/ha and 100 kg N/ha was applied in 4 equal splits at 10-d intervals after transplanting.

White Ponni yielded highest under all conditions (see table). ♂

Performance of White Ponni under transplanted and direct-seeded conditions, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Parentage	Samba 1984-85 ^a		Late Samba 1984-85 ^b	
		Days to flowering	Yield (t/ha)	Days to flowering	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Transplanted</i>					
White Ponni	TG65/ME80	100	3.1	100	4.0
Paiyur 1	IR1721-14/IR1330-3-3-2	105	3.0	103	3.3
PY 1	Ponni/IR8	100	2.5	103	3.3
Ponni	TC65/ME80	—	—	105	3.9
Co 43	Dasal/IR20	93	2.4	100	3.0
IR20	IR262ITKM6	98	2.4	98	3.8
<i>Direct-seeded^c</i>					
White Ponni	TG65/ME80	116	2.2		
Bam3	Bayyahunda-Pureline	93	1.2		
Co 31	GEB24/O. <i>perennis</i>	99	1.5		
IR20	IR262/TKM6	98	0.2		

^aSown 14 Aug, planted 8 Sep 1984, ^bSown 17 Oct, planted 23 Nov 1984. ^cSown 21 Sep 1984.

NLR9672 and NLR9674 released for cultivation in southern Andhra Pradesh

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NLR9672 and NLR9674, developed at ARS, are high yielding semidwarf rices that were released as Kotha Molagolukulu for cultivation in wet

season in Nellore, Prakasam, and parts of Cuddapah and Chittoor. Both are from the cross of Bulk H/9 and Milekkunung. Bulk H/9 is a selection from local Pedda Molagolukulu and has good grain quality. Milekkunung is a Malaysian variety with blast (BI) resistance.

NLR9672 matures in 160-170 d and NLR9674 in 170-180 d. They are weakly photoperiod-sensitive. NLR9674 has a droopy flag leaf, and NLR9672 has an erect flag leaf. They have good tillering

ability and produce many grains per panicle (Table 1). Both varieties have grain type similar to that of Molagolukulu, which is locally preferred. Grains are short and bold with white, translucent kernels and have excellent cooking and keeping qualities. Seed dormancy also is desirable. Both the varieties perform well, even if 60-d-old seedlings are planted late in wet season. NLR9672 is moderately resistant to B1 and bacterial blight, and NLR9674 is B1 resistant.

In five yield trials from 1970 to 1974 (Aug-Sep to Jan), NLR9672 followed by NLR9674 yielded significantly higher than Bulk H/9. In 1975 minikit trials at 20 sites in Nellore. NLR9672 yielded an average 17% and NLR9674 10% higher than Bulk H/9 (Table 2).

NLR9672 is grown on 250,000 ha and NLR9674 is on 200,000 ha in Nellore

Table 1. Agronomic traits of NLR9672 and NLR9674 at Nellore, India.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	1,000-grain wt (g)
NLR9672	160	100	248	339	23.5
NLR9674	170	104	269	326	22.5
BulkH/9	180	150	198	192	22.0

Table 2. Grain yields of NLR9672 and NLR9674 at Nellore, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)						1975 minikit trial ^a
	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	Mean	
NLR9672	5.4	5.7	6.1	3.8	4.4	5.1	4.0
NLR9674	5.2	5.7	5.9	3.5	4.1	4.9	3.7
BulkH/9	3.8	5.4	5.3	3.1	3.3	4.2	3.3
CD P = 0.05	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.5		

^a Mean of 20 locations.

and Prakasam and parts of Guntur, Cuddapah, and Chittoor. *J*

New varieties derived from BG96-2

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BG90-2 was developed in Sri Lanka. Introduced in China in 1976, it was released in Nanjing as a midseason variety in 1979 because it has excellent

morphoagronomic characters and high resistance to bacterial blight (RH). Its growth duration exceeds 150 d. however, which makes it difficult to grow after wheat. Several promising varieties or lines have been developed from BG90-2.

B-xuan 1 and B-fu 1 were selected from BG90-2 by the Jiangpu County Institute of Agricultural Sciences in 1979; 910 and Yang-dao 1 were developed by the Yangzhou District Institute of Agricultural Sciences,

Yangzhou. Jungsu Province, in 1980. B-xuan 1, 910, and Yang-dao 1 were derived from BG90-2 as pureline selections, but B-fu 1 was developed by irradiating BG90-2 seeds with Co⁶⁰ gamma rays. The new varieties and lines have shorter growth duration than BG90-2 and good characters (see table). They have been widely planted in Honan, Hubei, Anhui, and Jiangsu Provinces. By 1984 they had covered 400,000ha. *J*

Characteristics of varieties derived from BG90-2, Nanjing, China.

Variety	Height (cm)	Seeding to full heading (d)	Growth duration (d)	Panicle length (m)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Fertile grains/panicle (no.)	Sterility (%)	1,000-seed wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Reaction ^a to BB
B-xuan 1	107	102	136	28	131	102	22	30	8.8	R
910	100	103	137	28	136	100	27	29	8.6	R
Yang-dao 1	91	97	129	24	132	116	13	25	7.7	S
B-fu 1	106	95	126	26	111	98	12	36	7.6	R
BG90-2 (parent)	113	115	154	26	161	128	20	27	8.2	R

^a R = resistant, S = susceptible.

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.